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Title: **Maximizing Research Outreach: Visibility Tools In Library and Information Science**

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Abstract: This paper highlights the concept of research visibility, reason to make visibility of research output, approaches to make it more visible and its various tools. In this work, we come to know how researchers, Library and Information Science (LIS) professionals engage themselves and are connected to each other in this research world through the research visibility tools and making contribution to their respective discipline as well as to the society. All of these tools have unique qualities and functions that set them apart from one another, make them even more appealing to users, and increase the visibility of their work.

Keywords: Academic Social Networking, LIS, Research Visibility Tools, Social Media

1. Introduction:

The growth of social media and academic networking sites have brought immense change in the way research process have been done and the way people view it. Earlier, people faced difficulty in making their work reach out to people due to lack of development of research visibility tools which somehow may be the reason to which the development in the library could not be done as much as it should have been.

Rising of these visibility tools helps the LIS researchers to break all the barriers and make their output being more visible and accessible. Using social media tools presence, the researchers and their work to the online world. By successfully utilising and interacting with social media tools, a researcher can establish an online presence on academic social media sites. This leads to online Web activity. This promotes an attempt to acknowledge and consider academic standards for the usage of social networking platform with a research focus. (Arda, 2012). Researchers can create and provide research directly through e-profiles on online communities of researchers like academia.edu thanks to academic networking platforms. (Thelwall, 2014).

2. Objective of The Study:

- a. To be aware of the significance of LIS research's visibility.
- b. Determine the method for making research visible.
- c. To understand its various tools.
- d. To make people aware about the essence of research, its tools in the area of LIS.

3. Visibility and E-Visibility:

The term "visibility" describes the quality of being seen or noticed. The term "e-visibility" refers to the condition of being widely visible online. The conception of e-visibility encompasses a researcher's online presence, discoverability, and accessibility of their study output as an electronic research profile on the internet. (Adriaanse, 2017). By setting up an online research e-profile on academic networking sites and

linking research output, researchers can increase their visibility and discoverability by incorporating all necessary and correct research information. (Ward, 2015).

4. Why we should make our research visible?

The visibility of any research is very much important whether it be for scientific, educational, or other purposes. Without visibility there is no way to make a significant positive difference. In the research and it will be unable to reach to the desirable audience. Reaching to more audience means to get more citation. When people cite our paper our impact factor will increase which can make the research, and researchers' profile more visible to others.

Another reason is to gain prestige, reputation, professional visibility and access to resource. Visibility also helps a researcher to get an opportunity to make domestic as well as international cooperation.

5. Enhancing the visibility of research:

Conference is a great platform for any researcher to showcase and promote the research, and also get the opportunity to meet new people, experts, and to make connections with people having same area of interest which helps the researcher to discuss about the desired topic and gain new ideas, knowledge and boost confident.

Another way of enhancing the visibility is the researcher should carefully consider in which journal they are going to publish. Before publishing any research work a researcher must know whether it will be easily accessible or not, one must know whether the journal has open access suitable or not. Making the scholarly work open access is one of the best way to increase its visibility. Publishing the work in open access makes it available online and freely accessible and reach to the larger community. Sharing the data in a relevant platform helps other researcher to validate the work and helps to get further collaboration.

A researcher must have opened an account and created an author profile on a different academic social networking sites, including Academia and ResearchGate, Web of Science, to publish and run their work appropriately, just as it is necessary to create a profile to use and access social networking platforms like Instagram, WhatsApp, and Facebook. As research promotion at conferences was already covered, let's not forget about the widespread use of social media for promotion. It is very appropriate way to get connected with the people, showcasing the work whether in a short way or full where they can give feedback to each other's work, engage themselves by questioning, answering and discussing and keep themselves up-to-date in the field they wanted to be in.

6. Tools for making research visible:

It must be wish of every researcher to bring their work to the larger community, and to get more impact in their scholarly work for which it is important to create a tool for the researchers where they can share, publish their output and make it easily available to the people.

Numerous academic social networking sites, such as Academia.edu, ResearchGate, Mendeley, Science Open, LinkedIn, and bibliographic databases like Scopus and Web of Science are available. These are used as tool for visibility of a research that makes researchers to create their own profile, avail to communicate with each other, avail to give feedbacks, avail to cite the work and it also shows impact factor such as h-index, I-Index, I10 index and so on. Discussed below are some of its tools.

6.1 A networking site namely academia.edu, which is completely based on academics. This networking site enable researchers to create profile, upload their scholarly work, follow each other and gives messages and feedbacks. Researcher can keep track on their analytics. User can know when a person from their follow list publishes a paper through the notification feature on their respective site. This website's "import contact" feature lets users connect with one another through social networking sites like Twitter and Facebook, for example.

6.2 ResearchGate is among the best sites for boosting a research paper's visibility. This website for academic networking enables the researcher to share one's knowledge by publishing articles, posters, data and read the publication of other users. It makes researcher to get connected and gives opportunity to collaborate and put inquiries and retorts to one another regarding research works which is regarded one of the best ways to know others perspective on a specific topic. This shows researchers analytics where they can see their RG Score, h-index, Breakdown, Percentile.

6.3 LinkedIn, a platform for networking where people and businesses may interact to promote working relationships, employment possibilities, skill development, knowledge sharing, etc. Although LinkedIn is accessible to all professions, academic scholars have found it to be a useful tool over time. LinkedIn was established in 2002 and runs on the www.linkedin.com website and mobile application. (Lawal, 2017).

6.4 Google Scholar is a search engine tool that specialises in identifying academic resources. It enables users to do comprehensive academic literature searches using data from scholarly websites, institutional libraries, university repositories, professional societies, and periodicals. Users can save their articles in Scholar Library and import their citations after creating a Scholar profile. Authors may easily keep track of their citations to their articles using Google Scholar's Citations function. Additionally, it offers a metrics function that makes it simple for authors to assess the influence and visibility of recent papers in scientific publications (Lawal, 2017).

6.5 Researcher Identifier, when a researcher's name is mistakenly written wrong, or when a researcher's changes its name. Basically, it happens with female researchers. Some people change their surname. Changes or any kind of incorrectness in the name makes difficulty while finding the research in any database which leads the visibility of a researcher decrease automatically. So, it is the Research identifier such as ORCID, ResearcherID, Scopus Author Identifier, International Standard Name Identifier (ISNI), Google Scholar Personal Profile etc. that helps researchers in this matter. It makes the researcher to find the research easily and check how often the article have been cited, this enables the visibility of a researcher and their work.

6.6 Social Media Networking Site: There are many social media sites like Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, Twitter, etc. a researcher can use these media as a tool to showcase their research work but using some of these tools to regularly create contents like videos, posts, slides etc. might be time consuming. In spite of getting confused while selecting sites relevant to them, a researcher must themselves figure out which of these social media sites are the best and appropriate platform to increase their visibility of research work as Twitter is consider one of the good platforms to showcase the work by publishing micro videos, or by tweeting about the latest research and providing links of the work in the tweet and so on. Facebook helps the researcher in the same way as twitter does but its features are different. Also, a

researcher can use various blogging platform like Blogger, Medium, Joomla, Tumblr, and WordPress where they can share their knowledge of work and their links to make their work known to people.

Any researcher can keep themselves updated in their area of interest by using social media. To attract their followers and makes their work known to the people a researcher must like and follow the pages of their desired field and specialist and must update contents regularly. This increases their visibility of work as these social media tools uses Altimetric to measure their research impact factor.

With the implementation of new technical innovations in libraries, it makes the LIS professionals to be more up to date with the recent trends, made them experts in handling in-house operations which leads library services/functions more systematically and smoothly. In this, the credit goes to the LIS researcher who brought all these in front of us.

7. Conclusion:

Research Visibility Tools are boosting platform for the researcher as they can make their output more visible and can receive enough citation with increase their impact of research. Research impact is inevitable for researcher to improve research reputation, increase institutional ranking and getting grand for funders. Academic social networking and social media platform both plays a crucial role to dissemination of findings, publishing the research output and lastly make contribution to their respective discipline and society as well.

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